

Synthesis, characterisation and coordination properties of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB) : Cobalt(III), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with a NNS donor system

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Abstract : The title ligand, 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (abbreviated as HMPzNB) has been synthesised and physicochemically characterised by elemental analysis, IR, PMR and mass spectrum. The ligational behaviour of the pyrazole-derived thiosemicarbazone, HMPzNB, has been examined by isolation and characterisation of its complexes with Co^{III}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with different counterions. Elemental analyses, magnetic and spectral features indicate [Co(MPzNB)₂]X (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻ or BF₄⁻) as the diamagnetic octahedral species with the ligand in the deprotonated thiol form, while [Ni(HMPzNB)₂]X₂ (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ or ClO₄⁻) is proposed as octahedral complex with the ligand in the neutral "thione" form. However, in the neutral condition (pH ~ 6) nickel(II) salt affords octahedral bis-nickel(II) complex, Ni(MPzNB)₂, while copper(II) salt gives [Cu(MPzNB)]X (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ or ClO₄⁻), with the deprotonated ligand. 5-Methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone possesses in its structure, the tertiary nitrogen atom (²N) of the pyrazole ring, the azomethine nitrogen and the sulphur atom as potential binding sites; thus the title ligand is expected to behave as a potential NNS tridentate during complex formation with a metal ion.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazones, cobalt(III), nickel(II), copper(II), cyclic voltammetry.

Thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes have been intensively studied in recent years owing to their biological interest¹.

In continuation of our studies² on the coordinating properties of biologically potent pyrazole-derived ligands, we now report the synthesis and spectroscopic characterisation of cobalt(III), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes derived from 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

HMPzNB has been characterised by elemental analyses (C, H and N), IR, PMR and mass spectral data. The available PMR and mass spectral data point to the structural formulation of HMPzNB as either **1a** or **1b**.

Cobalt(III) complexes : The general composition is [Co(MPzNB)₂]X (where X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻ or BF₄⁻). The conductivity measurements of the complexes in DMF afford Λ_m values in the range 65–90 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1) indicating 1 : 1 electrolytes. The electronic spectral data of cobalt(III) complexes both in solid and in solution are given in the Table 1 and the results are similar as reported by other workers^{3,4}. Electronic spectra in DMF of all the reported cobalt(III) complexes show three bands in the range 40325–36675 and 24200–23855 cm^{-1} ascribed to intra ligand charge transfer and *d-d* transitions respectively.

Nickel(II) complexes : With the ligand, HMPzNB, have the general composition [Ni(HMPzNB)₂]X₂ (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻

^ψDeceased.

Table 1. Analytical, conductance and magnetic moment data for the complexes of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB)

Complex (Color)	Analysis ^a (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff}^a	Λ^b	State	Intra-ligand charge transfer	Frequencies (log ϵ L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) <i>d</i> → <i>d</i> transition
	C	H	N	M					
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Cl (Brown)	49.1 (48.9)	4.4 (4.4)	22.6 (21.9)	9.4 (9.2)	Diam.	72.3	Solid	-	25100, 12090 9750, 8602
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Br (Reddish brown)	44.2 (45.7)	4.7 (4.1)	18.9 (20.5)	8.90 (8.62)	Diam.	71.2	Solid	-	24752, 11720 9775, 8520
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]NO ₃ (Deep brown)	46.9 (46.9)	5.0 (4.2)	22.3 (23.2)	8.9 (8.9)	Diam.	73.1	Solid	-	24570, 11720 8810, 8475
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]ClO ₄ (Deep brown)	44.6 (44.4)	4.0 (4.0)	20.4 (19.9)	8.7 (8.4)	Diam.	75.5	Solid	-	23980, 11740 10152, 8525
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]BF ₄ (Brown)	45.1 (45.2)	4.2 (4.0)	22.1 (20.3)	8.72 (8.5)	Diam.	75.1	Solid	-	24770, 11850 9220, 8530
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂]Cl ₂ (Parrot green)	45.92 (46.17)	4.28 (4.43)	20.22 (20.71)	8.92 (8.68)	2.79	142.2	Solid	-	27470, 17450 11835
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂]Br ₂ (Deep green)	41.10 (40.81)	3.78 (3.92)	18.11 (18.31)	7.92 (7.67)	2.84	145.1	Solid	-	32570, 28090, 17830, 12330 27500, 17510 11940
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Green)	42.66 (42.81)	4.01 (4.11)	20.22 (21.13)	8.31 (8.05)	3.12	146.0	Solid	-	32600, 27950, 17770, 12210 27650, 17630 11840
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂]I ₂ (Light green)	36.22 (36.34)	3.91 (3.49)	15.54 (16.30)	7.23 (6.83)	2.93	141.6	Solid	-	32415, 28110, 17760, 12020 27670, 17570 11660
[Ni(MPzNB) ₂] (Reddish green)	51.62 (51.76)	4.66 (4.64)	22.84 (23.22)	9.60 (9.74)	2.90	- 20.22	Solid	-	32505, 28100, 17670, 11990 28650, 20445 11440
[Cu(MPzNB)Cl] (Green)	42.2 (42.0)	3.7 (3.8)	17.5 (18.9)	18.2 (17.1)	2.30	20.22	Solid	24690	32570, 29150, 22330, 11890 14925
[Cu(MPzNB)Br] (Bright green)	37.7 (37.6)	3.2 (3.3)	16.1 (16.9)	16.8 (15.3)	1.78	23.10	Solid	32260	16130
[Cu(MPzNB)NO ₃] (Parrot green)	40.1 (39.3)	3.6 (3.5)	20.3 (21.1)	16.5 (15.9)	1.83	17.70	Solid	24330	14490
[Cu(MPzPyr)ClO ₄] (Deep green)	36.4 (35.9)	3.3 (3.2)	15.7 (16.0)	15.5 (14.6)	1.73	16.51	Solid	32790	16390
							Solid	24720	14860
							Solid	25210	15100
							Solution	32790	15455

^a $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.83\sqrt{10^6\chi_M T}$ at 298 K.^bMolar conductivity (Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) of ca. 10⁻³ M solution in DMF.

or NO₃⁻) with the exception of [Ni(MPzNB)₂]. The molar conductance values in DMF are indicative of 1 : 2

electrolytic nature, while the [Ni(MPzNB)₂] is non-electrolyte in the same solvent. The magnetic moment values

(Table 1) for all the reported bis-species of nickel(II) fall within the range 2.79–3.10 B.M. indicating six-coordinate spin free nickel(II) complexes. The diffuse reflectance spectral bands (Table 1) are consistent with octahedral structure of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones⁵.

Copper(II) complexes : The copper(II) complexes with HMPzNB, have the general composition [Cu(MPzNB)X] (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ or ClO₄⁻) (Table 1). The magnetic moment values are in the range 1.73–2.03 B.M. (*d⁹* system). The DMF solutions of the reported complexes furnish molar conductance values of 16.0–23.0 Ω⁻¹ cm²

mol⁻¹ suggesting their non-electrolytic nature. The electronic spectra of the complexes (Table 1) are dominated by the intra-ligand (π → π* or n → π*) and charge transfer transitions in the high energy regions. However, the spectra has one low intensity broad band in the region ca. 15000 cm⁻¹ both in solid and solution spectra being recognized as the usual *d-d* band for Cu^{II}. The electronic spectra of [Cu(MPzNB)X] (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ and ClO₄⁻) is also similar as reported earlier^{3,4}.

IR spectral data (Table 2), PMR data (Table 3) and ESR spectral parameters (Table 4) of all complexes indi-

Table 2. Some characteristic IR bands (in cm⁻¹) of the metal complexes of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{CH=N(azom)}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N(pz)}}$	$\nu_{\text{N-N(pz)}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N(pz)}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N(azom)}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-S}}$
HMPzNB	1550	1505	1010	800	–	–	–
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Cl	1520	1560	1060	700	204	507	268
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Br	1488	1526	1070	696	206	509	268
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]NO ₃	1486	1520	1050	696	206	504	280
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]ClO ₄	1490	1515	1050	700	206	504	278
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]BF ₄	1496	1520	1050	680	204	510	280
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂]Cl ₂	1485	1580	1030	705	270	480	365
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂]Br ₂	1485	1575	1035	700	275	476	370
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	1490	1580	1040	700	265	480	360
[Ni(HMPzNB) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1480	1575	1030	710	270	478	360
[Ni(MPzNB) ₂]	1490	1580	1035	705	265	470	350
[Cu(MPzNB)Cl]	1480	1585	1040	700	280	510	330
[Cu(MPzNB)Br]	1480	1580	1050	700	280	470	340
[Cu(MPzNB)NO ₃]	1480	1580	1040	710	275	485	335
[Cu(MPzNB)ClO ₄]	1480	1590	1035	700	270	490	340

Table 3. PMR assignments of the ligand HMPzNB and its cobalt(III) complexes (in δ ppm) relative to TMS

Compd.	Imino proton	Position of protons pyrazolyl ring			Methine proton	Benzylic proton	Benzene ring protons
		1	4	5			
HMPzNB	11.68 8.00	12.87	6.34	2.26	7.87	4.79	7.29
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Cl	–	13.76	6.46	2.46	8.40	4.50	7.24
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]Br	–	13.76	6.48	2.44	8.40	4.50	7.24
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]NO ₃	–	13.78	6.48	2.46	8.40	4.54	7.26
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]ClO ₄	–	13.80	6.52	2.44	8.40	4.48	7.26
[Co(MPzNB) ₂]BF ₄	–	13.78	6.50	2.46	8.40	4.50	7.26

Table 4. ESR spectral parameters for copper(II) complexes of HMPzNB

Compd.	<i>g</i>	<i>g</i> _⊥	<i>g</i> _{average}
[Cu(MPzNB)Cl]	2.10	2.02	2.05
[Cu(MPzNB)Br]	2.14	2.03	2.10
[Cu(MPzNB)NO ₃]	2.12	2.06	2.08
[Cu(MPzNB)ClO ₄]	2.12	2.04	2.06

cate towards same structural assignments.

The CV profile of the present Cu^{II} complexes (Table 5) are quite similar to those of the analogous compounds prepared with the related 2-acetyl pyridine ⁴N-dialkylthiosemicarbazone⁶. To facilitate discussion, all the reduction and oxidation peaks of the CV have been identified (Fig. 2) and denoted by capital letters A, C, E and F.

Table 5. Cyclic voltammetric data for the copper(II) complexes of the ligand HMPzNB in DMSO solution containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate on a Pt electrode at a scan rate of 100 mV/s

Compd.	E_p (A)	E_p (C)	$E_{1/2}^0$	i_{pa}/i_{pc}	E_p (E)	E_p (F)
[Cu(MPzNB)Cl]	-0.486	-0.342	-0.414	0.94	+0.250	+0.380
[Cu(MPzNB)Br]	-0.529	-0.455	-0.492	0.81	+0.307	+0.267

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of copper(II) complexes of HMPzNB in a 0.1 (M) solution of $[Bu^4N]ClO_4$ in DMSO.

The two peaks represent the reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu^I , (A); and the subsequent oxidation of Cu^I to Cu^{II} , (C). The separation between peak A and C within the scan rate employed is characteristic of an apparent quasi-reversible one electron process probably due to stereochemical change from planar Cu^{II} to tetrahedral copper(I). The reduction of the conjugated portion of the coordinated thiosemicarbazone ligand at *ca.* +0.25 V (E), is comparable with values observed for many reported

thiosemicarbazone ligands⁷.

Experimental

(i) *Preparation of the ligand and complexes* : The title ligand has been synthesised for the first time following a method⁸ which involved (i) preparation of *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(5-methylpyrazole-3-yl)methylenedithio-carbazate (say HMPzSMe) as reported earlier² and (ii) the conversion to 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴*N*-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB) by transamination reaction of HMPzSMe and benzyl amine base. Finally the ligand, HMPzNB, was obtained by refluxing 2.14 g (0.01 mol) of HMPzSMe (recrystallised product) in 30 cm³ absolute ethanol (99.9%) with *ca.* 1 cm³ of freshly distilled benzyl amine for 12 h at water bath temperature (Caution! the evolution of poisonous CH_3SH gas occurs). (a) When reflux was over, the resulting solution was taken in a beaker and the volume was reduced to at least 1/3 of its original one upon slow evaporation; a white crystalline solid obtained was filtered off and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (yield *ca.* 80%). The recrystallised product melted sharply at 199 °C (Found : C, 56.88; H, 5.74; N, 25.40. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{15}N_5S$: C, 57.35; H, 5.49; N, 25.73%).

(ii) *Preparation of bis-cobalt(III) complexes* : $[Co(MPzNB)_2]X$ (where $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$ and BF_4^-) : To a solution of the ligand (0.005 mol, 1.37 g) in ethanol (40 cm³) was added a solution (30 cm³) of the hydrated cobalt(II) salt (0.0025 mol) in the same solvent; air was passed through this solution for one hour. Dark/reddish brown crystals precipitated out slowly during the process of oxidation. The crystals, in each case were filtered off and washed with aqueous ethanol (70%) and dried over silica gel (yield 60–70%).

(iii) *Preparation of bis-nickel(II) complexes* : $[Ni(HMPzNB)_2]X_2$ (where $X = Cl^-, Br^-$ and NO_3^-) : A hot ethanolic solution (40 cm³) of the hydrated nickel(II) salts (0.0025 mol) was mixed with a solution (50 cm³) of the ligand (0.005 mol, 1.37 g) in the same solvent. The resulting solution was filtered off and the clear green solution was warmed on water bath and kept at room temperature (~ 25 °C) overnight. The desired complexes, in each case, separated out as microcrystalline colored species. The greenish crystalline complexes were filtered off, washed with alcohol and dried over silica gel. The complexes were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (70%) to have the analytically pure samples (yield 70–75%).

(iv) *Preparation of bis-complexes of nickel(II) with the deprotonated ligand* $[Ni(MPzNB)_2]$: A hot alcoholic solution of hydrated nickel(II) chloride (0.0025 mol, 0.59

g) was mixed with a solution (40 cm³) of the ligand (0.005 mol, 1.37 g) in the same solvent and to the resulting solution, dilute aqueous ammonia was added dropwise until ammoniacal. The solution was then warmed with constant stirring on water bath to remove excess ammonia (pH of the resulting solution was ca. 6.5) and concentrated to half of its original volume. Brown microcrystalline compound separated out upon standing overnight. The complex was filtered off, washed thoroughly with aqueous ethanol (70%) and dried over silica gel (yield ca. 50%).

(v) *Preparation of the mono-complexes of copper(II) : [Cu(MPzNB)X] (where X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ and ClO₄⁻) :* The ligand (0.0025 mol, 0.68 g) dissolved in methanol (50 cm³) was mixed with a solution of the appropriate copper(II) salt (0.0025 mol) in the same solvent (25 cm³) and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 5–10 min. The desired mono-complexes generally crystallised out of reaction mixture on cooling to room temperature (~25 °C). The complex, in each case, was collected by filtration, washed with aqueous ethanol (70%) and dried as before. The perchlorate complex of copper(II) was hygroscopic in nature and was kept in a vacuum dessicator over anhydrous CaCl₂ (yield ca. 50%).

Conclusion :

On the basis of the available physicochemical parameters and the discussion made, it may reasonably be concluded that the ligand, HMPzNB, coordinates with cobalt(III) and copper(II) as mono deprotonated NNS tridentate through the tertiary ring nitrogen (²N), azomethine nitrogen and thiolato sulphur atom. The uni-negative tridenticity of the ligand has been demonstrated also in forming monomeric Ni(MPzNB)₂ at pH ≈7, however,

the other electrolytic nickel(II) complexes of general composition [Ni(HMPzNB)₂]X₂ are formed by the interaction of nickel(II) salts and the ligand (HMPzNB) in its neutral tridentate form with same NNS donor sites.

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